

THE ESSENTIAL ROLE OF TEACHERS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A PUPIL'S LIFE

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with teachers' role in shaping the future of their pupils. Different approaches were given to motivate pupils to learn language easily and they were analyzed in a deep way. Some effective ways in which teachers can encourage students were proved. Examples were also illustrated in order to prove ideas efficiently. In addition, the influence of teachers are not limited only within the classroom but their different roles can be seen even outside the classroom. The teacher's role is described beyond teaching.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a very fundamental and vital role in shaping the future of their students. At the beginning of the early life, children go to the kindergarten, then attend to school and college or lyceum and eventually enroll university, they are the ones who teach knowledge and explain pupils about everything important. Moreover, they also teach pupils about decent standards in moral values. Therefore, it is true that teachers outline our personality into something extremely durable and magnificent. A world without teachers would be definitely confusing. There are only a few people in our lives who can influence our sphere, it is admitted that teachers are absolutely one of them. They assume the role of an instructor and caregiver for their students. Sometimes, they also become our supporters and aid us with personal difficulties. A teacher is considered as the one who will assist you become an intelligent, a full of common-sense person and a knowledgeable one. As soon as a child is admitted to school, the role of a teacher is to shape the life the child commences. Teachers are characterized as guides to show the bright future and choose a proper way of crossing in our life to succeed in a career, job, business, and especially making a lucky human being. A good teacher helps us to become good human beings in society and good citizens of the country. For the reason that teachers know that young generation are the future of each nation.

Moreover, they see the potential of their students when no one else can. Teachers also decide the fate of a nation as the youth is in their hands. When the youth is educated and informed, naturally, the future of the country will be in safe hands. In fact, the fate of students is in the hands of their teachers. They push the students to achieve greater heights and

become successful. Consequently, they turn out to be doctors, lawyers, pilots, scientists and more, only with the help of a teacher. In Uzbekistan, we even celebrate Teacher's Day to honor them on 1st October, every year. It is one of the greatest holidays that is based on appreciating and respecting towards teachers. Everyone congratulate their best teachers on the occasion of holiday and wish good luck, strong health, much happiness. Sometimes they may give special gifts for their teachers. Indeed, hard as well as challenging labor of teachers is worth praising and applauding as much as possible.

As a matter of fact, allotted hours of the lessons is the main source to educate and teach behavior of norms for teachers. Through traditional classes and extracurricular learning such as art, music, dance, drama, public speaking, and sports, teachers help children to become more creative, self-reliant, and resilient. Discerning teachers take the time to understand the strengths and weaknesses of each child under their care and guide them to develop their characters, push their limits, and become better and more optimistic human beings. They provide them with the foundation they need to have well-adjusted personal lives and to make useful contributions to the society they live in. They enable them to form their own opinions, influence others, and have a positive impact on shaping the future of their world. As teachers influence and shape the personalities of the future members of society, they eventually become responsible for how future generations go forward.

There are a lot of types of teachers. One of them is a motivated teacher who encourages their pupils to study harder and accomplish success during entire life. A motivated teacher is very important to the classroom as they have various beneficial approaches to teaching than others. They also motivate their students to learn in a fun and engaging manner. Motivation is one of the strongest tools that keeps children positive through a long period of time. It involves working toward goals and tailoring activities to achieve this purpose. It helps in driving creativity and curiosity among students. It is not just about getting the students motivated at the moment, but it also involves developing their underlying goals and aspirations through their academic journey. Here are some effective ways in which teachers can motivate students and be the perfect teachers for them.

1. Encourage Students: To encourage and motivate in an appropriate way makes an essential role in teaching. Students often look at their teachers for approval and are more likely to be enthusiastic about learning if they feel that their work is valued and recognized. Open communication and free thinking can do wonders for the students and make them voice their opinions with confidence. A "good job" can go a long way.

2. Make Learning Fun: Teachers have to conduct a captivating and an interesting lesson in order to attract the attention of the pupils to the new topic. If lesson seems fun and clear, pupils easily understand it. So, teachers should always make their classes interesting and fun instead of explaining concepts through lectures in a very technical fashion. Try including game-based learning and competitions to get students more involved and alert at all times. This will definitely create interest among students and give them an opportunity to interact with each other.

3. Draw Connections To Real Life: It is a good way to use real samples and illustrate each topic with details in order to prove mentioned approaches. While studying different subjects, students often wonder if they will ever make use of the knowledge in real life? They

generally believe that what they are learning is not important and has no purpose. A good teacher should cite examples and demonstrate how the subject relates to everyday life and how it can be used in the future.

4. **Set Performance Goals:** To teach planning and setting a goal before starting any task is an effective method of teachers. Teachers can help students by setting small achievable goals and encourage them to complete their goals. It is efficient to design assignments that are challenging but they should be relevant according to the aptitude of the class.

5. **Change Scenery:** A classroom is definitely a great place for learning, but sitting at the desk all day and learning can become a tedious affair for the students, as well as the teachers. Giving students a chance to get out of the classroom and learn in a new environment gets them interested and motivated. You would be surprised at the benefits of a new setting or open classroom!

6. **Step Away From Textbooks:** Bringing in material that your students can connect with, and that matches their needs and interests can improve the lesson output. Create activities and games to show them that you are also prepared to put in a lot of effort that will help them to succeed.

7. **Don't Over-Correct:** Students shouldn't be corrected repeatedly when they are speaking in front of the class. If they are interrupted intermittently, they will lose their confidence. After they have completed, you should motivate them and then point out the major mistakes they might have made. You can always tell them that making mistakes is a natural part of learning and evolving.

8. **Hand Over Some Control:** If the students take ownership of how the classroom activities are carried out, they will feel happy and relaxed. Take an audit of your class, by asking students what they enjoy, what helps them learn, what they're excited about after class. After reviewing the answers, integrate their ideas into the classroom sessions and witness the increase in student engagement.

9. **Track Improvement:** Always remind students that they have come a long way from where they started. Set short-term goals, emphasize improvement, keep self-evaluation forms to fill out and compare throughout the year. This helps them monitor their progress and acts as a confidence booster.

10. **Allow Students To Work Together:** When students work together, they often try to solve problems while having fun! Collaboration is a great teaching tool in itself. Teachers, however, to ensure that the groups are balanced and fair so that some students aren't doing more work than the others. While a deep and broad knowledge of the subject is essential for being a good teacher, a lot also depends on how the knowledge is passed on to the students. The focus should not be on learning notes and securing marks but on a lucid understanding of the subject and holistic development of the child. A teacher is a nurturer and her role goes beyond academics, she is responsible for creating a love for life-long learning and advancement.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, I would restate that the role of a teacher is not limited to only the classroom but their different roles can be seen even outside the classroom. The teacher's role is described beyond teaching. They are more than an educator and are counsellors, mentors,

role models, external parents, and so on to a student. There are many significant ways that provide a better understanding of a lesson to help students in a better future.

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